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The Effects of Digital Learning and Compensation On Teacher Performance in Tangerang City

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Abstrak

Teacher performance is important in relation to the quality of education. Compensation is one of the reasons for having motivation to improve. This research method is a quantitative method. Data was collected through filling out questionnaires and interviews. Data processing using SPSS 25. Data variables X1 (compensation), X2 (digital learning) and Y (teacher performance). The sample was 50 teachers in the city of Tangerang, Banten. Compensation influences teacher performance in the city of Tangerang, digital learning influences teacher performance, and compensation and digital learning influences teacher performance. Heads and education managers can provide appropriate compensation, so that teachers are able to perform well and have adequate digital skills.

Key words: *compensation, digital learning, teacher performance*

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PENDAHULUAN

Teacher performance is still an obstacle to improving the quality of education. Performance is related to the compensation received by teachers. Compensation is the teacher's right, if they can achieve the specified performance targets. This type of compensation has the ability to encourage teacher motivation in terms of supervision, work performance, and loyalty to the institution. In terms of providing compensation, it is necessary to pay attention to the extent of this compensation, because the amount of compensation will affect their performance. Although compensation does not have a direct impact on performance, there are other factors that influence teacher work results. Work motivation is one of the reasons why it can be an intermediate factor in teacher performance.

Bantolo (2023) in this research, concluded that employee performance is influenced by compensation and the level of job satisfaction, while work motivation acts as a factor that influences the relationship between the level of job satisfaction and employee performance. The most influential factors in this research are compensation and job satisfaction. The results show that compensation has a significant impact on performance, especially when moderated by work motivation, indicating that compensation has a close correlation with work motivation, which in turn influences individual performance. Apart from compensation, as the age of information systems advances, digital learning has become an inevitable necessity.

Digital learning is a system that allows students to learn with a wider scope and richer variations, including various types of learning material, not only in verbal form, but also involving text, visual elements, audio and movement elements (Pontis, 2020). Teachers have various choices of learning media that can be used in the classroom, including interactive multimedia, digital video and animation, podcasts, Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, and game-based learning (Blevins, 2018). Teachers can choose from various types of learning media that can be applied in the classroom, such as interactive multimedia, digital video and animation, podcasts, Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, and game-based learning (Baali, et al. 2023)

Learning materials are now becoming more diverse, not only limited to verbal form, but including variations such as text, visual elements, audio and movement. The development of education in the digital era has opened access to wider knowledge. Changes in education in the digital era require teachers to have the ability to integrate information and communication

technology in the learning process. The digital learning approach also allows students to learn independently and develop autonomous learning abilities.

The use of digital technology in the education sector has experienced an evolution starting with the use of audio visual aids (AVA) to deliver learning material in the classroom. Then, developments continued with the use of computers as a tool for accessing and managing information, with software that facilitates the processing and exchange of information. (Munir, 2017). This development creates a change in the views of Purdy and Wright (1992). Differences in learning pattern paradigms emerge when comparing learning that does not adopt technology with learning that utilizes technology. Likewise, there is a paradigm shift between the concept of learning in a traditional classroom setting and open or digital-based learning that is not limited to the physical classroom environment. Furthermore, Munir (2017), from the perspective of digital learning models, there are significant differences in teaching styles, teaching techniques, and motivation that influence both learners and teachers. The digital learning model is considered an effective future learning model because it is in accordance with technological demands. To implement digital learning, a teacher, such as a teacher, must have a variety of competencies which include learning planning and organization, verbal and nonverbal presentation skills, collaboration with fellow teachers, skills in question and answer strategies, mastery of learning material, learner involvement in the learning process, coordination of learning activities, understanding of learning theory, knowledge of digital learning, knowledge of learning planning, and proficiency in using the learning media used. (Crystal, 1997).

Based on the description above, the research question that can be asked is whether there is an influence of compensation on teacher performance and whether there is an influence of digital learning on teacher performance. The aim of the research is to determine the effect of compensation on teacher performance and to determine the effect of digital learning on teacher performance.

METHOD

This research method is a quantitative method. Data was collected through filling out questionnaires and interviews. Process the data using SPSS 25. Data variables X1 (compensation), X2 (digital learning) and Y (Teacher performance). The sample was 50 teachers in the city of Tangerang, Banten. . Data were tested for assumptions with normality and collinearity. Next, it is processed into the coefficient of determination and multiple regression analysis, T test and F test (Anova).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Questionnaire results from 3 variables, variables X1, X2 and Y. Data collection was taken from the questionnaire. Process the data entered into SPSS 25.

Table 1 Collinearity Statistic

Model	Collinearity Statistic	
	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)		
Compensation	.674	1.214
Digital Learning	.674	1.314

VIF is a factor that measures how much the variance of the regression estimator coefficient increases compared to independent variables that are orthogonal if connected linearly. The VIF value will be greater if there is a greater correlation between the independent variables. If the VIF value exceeds 10 then this shows that collinearity is a problem that definitely occurs between independent variables.

Tests of Normality

Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a		Shapiro-Wilk			
Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.

Teacher Performance (Y)	.154	25	.017	.937	25	.018
Compensation (X1)	.148	25	.016	.947	25	.021
Digital Learning (X2)	.101	25	.*	.967	25	.156

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.
 a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

In the data normality test table above, the Sig value can be seen. the learning outcomes are $0.17 > 0.05$, the creativity value is $0.16 > 0.005$ and the self-confidence value is $0.210 > 0.05$, which means the data has a normal distribution.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	110.690	11.637		9.512	.000
	Compensation (X1)	-.104	.116	-.122	-.903	.391
	Digital Learning (X2)	-.219	.077	-.383	-2.842	.066

a. Dependent Variable: Teacher_Performance(Y)

In the coefficient table above, the Sig value can be seen. Compensation is $0.391 > 0.05$, meaning that the creativity variable influences craft and entrepreneurship learning outcomes. and, digital learning variable has effect on teacher performance, the Sig. $0.66 < 0.05$.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	683.305	2	341.652	4.099	.013
	Residual	4083.772	49	83.342		
Total		4767.077	51			

a. Dependent Variable: Teacher_Performance(Y)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Compensation (X1), Digital_learning (X1)

In the Anova table, the Sig value. $0.013 < 0.05$ means that there is an influence of variable X1 and variable X2 on teacher performance.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.379 ^a	.443	.108	9.12920

a. Predictors: (Constant), Compensation (X1), Digital_Learning (X2)

In the R Square table, it is 0.443, which means that there is an influence of 44.3%, X1 and X2 on Y. This value is intended for the influence of X1 and X2 on Y simultaneous.

DISCUSSION

Research shows that compensation and digital learning influence teacher performance in Tangerang City. Digital learning is a concern for more advanced learning methods, this is in

accordance with Dopo, F. B., & Ismaniati, C. (2016) who stated that digital literacy competencies are important to face the era of digitalization.

In connection with efforts to improve the quality of education, teachers are required to be professional in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. This is stated in the law that teachers are professional educators who are obliged to continuously improve academic qualifications and competencies in line with developments in science, technology and art (Herlianto et al., 2018). With the rapid development of technology, currently a professional teacher is required to understand and master digital technology to support a teacher's abilities (Montolalu & Langi, 2018).

In current technological developments, teachers' abilities in learning have been greatly helped by digital technology, access to information can be obtained easily, so that information and the implementation of learning are greatly helped. The existence of these various conveniences appears to be both an opportunity and a challenge. Opportunities to improve the quality of learning and challenges for teachers to continue to improve their own skills, especially efforts to master technology. Teachers must have various 21st century skills, one of which is using and collaborating technology in delivering and supporting the education system. Teachers need to develop digital learning resources for students to access using technology, teachers and students must use digital technology to facilitate learning.

CONCLUSION

Compensation influences teacher performance in the city of Tangerang, digital learning influences teacher performance, and compensation and digital learning influence teacher performance. Heads and education managers can provide appropriate compensation, so that teachers are able to perform well and have adequate digital skills.

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